

Legal Protection for users of Air Transport Services in Domestic Flights

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Abstract

The method used in this research is the method of normative legal research with the type of data in the form of primary legal materials composed of Law No. 1 of 2009 on Flights, Law No. 8 of 1999 on Consumer Protection and Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 Year 2011 On Responsibility Carrier Air Transport. Secondary legal materials in these study flight expert opinions, findings in the field based experience, while the non-legal materials are flight dictionary. Techniques of collecting legal material carried by the literature search and experience of the researchers themselves.

Results of this study found that the rules regarding the provision of special facilities for the disabled, the elderly, children under the age of 12 (twelve) years old and the sick are not found in domestic flights in Indonesia. The procedure for obtaining compensation to the passengers who died as a result of an aircraft accident is very convoluted. In addition the results of this study found that the compensation to the passengers due to flight delays has not been optimally implemented.

Keywords: legal protection, air transport services

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Geographically, by area and population spread, the role and function of air transport in Indonesia has a very important position and also strategically, both in terms of unity and national unity, social and cultural life, the economy, the wheels of government as well as defense and security. Air transport is the only alternative that is fast, efficient and economical for the transportation between islands and between regions in Indonesia.

In addition, air transport is also an important tool for the development of tourism, considering Indonesia as one of the few countries that are rich in culture and natural beauty that is attractive and tropical climate to attract foreign tourists bringing in foreign exchange as a substitute for petroleum is increasingly degenerate.

The role and function of air transport is very important, especially in terms of politics and the economy has led to very rapid development of the national aviation world. This development not only in the number of aircraft, but also in the number of companies operating in Indonesia

Given the importance of air transport in Indonesia, it is necessary to give more attention to the users of air transport services; particularly in this paper is a passenger. Attention in question is the form of good service, given the mode of transport is costly, both to establish an airline, or for the user to

operate transport services also requires regular large enough to be able to use these transport modes. Services needed by users of air transport services are:

- a. Associated with good service; and
- b. The right to receive compensation if losses.

The second form of service required by the users of air transport services is an essential requirement that must be met by the air carrier.

1.2 Problems

Problems that become the focus in this study are:

- a. Application of good service in a mode of air transportation in Indonesia.
- b. Application of the compensation provided to passengers when experiencing loss.

1.3 Research Methods

The method used in this research is the method of normative legal research with the type of data in the form of primary legal materials composed of Law No. 8 of 1999 on Consumer Protection, Law No. 1 Year 2009 on Aviation and the Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 Year 2011 Responsibilities of Air Transport Carrier. Secondary legal materials in this study are the opinions of legal experts and the author's personal experiences (participative methods), whereas non-legal material is in the form of Flight Dictionary. The technique of collecting legal material carried by the literature search and field studies.

2. Research Result

2.1 Conceptual Basis

Runway departure legal protection for the people (public or consumer / service user) in Indonesia is Pancasila and the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (the 1945 NRI 1945), because it is the basis of ideology and philosophy of the Indonesian nation that upholds humanitarian values by placing law as commander and not power. Respect for human rights and the position of Indonesia as a country whose legal consequences must be adhered to and implemented by the government as state officials.

AZ. Nasution¹, interpret consumer protection as "the overall principles and rules that regulate and protect consumers in the relationship and the problem with the providers of goods and / or services the consumer." Furthermore, Az. Nasution said that consumer protection laws are part of the load consumer law principles or rules are set, and Also Contain properties that protect the interests of consumers. The consumer law is defined as the overall principles and rules of law governing the relationship and problems between the various parties with each other with regard to consumer goods and services, in social life.² The notion put forward by these experts affirmed in Article 1 paragraph 1 UUPK, that consumer protection is all the effort that guarantee legal certainty to provide protection to consumers.

One function of law is to provide protection to citizens, especially those who are in a weak position due to a legal relationship that is not balanced. Likewise with the Consumer Protection Law to protect consumers from dishonest businesses.

Consumer protection is all the effort that guarantee legal certainty to provide protection to consumers. While the Consumer Protection Law is the overall principles and rules that regulate and protect consumers in the relationship and delivery problems and the use of consumer products between providers and users of public life.

Regarding businesses, the general public usually refer to businesses as manufacturers. Sometimes they interpret producers as entrepreneurs, but there is also the argument that the only

¹ Az Nasution, 1999, Consumer Protection, An Introduction, Daya Widya, Jakarta, 1999, p. 3

² *Ibid*, p. 3

manufacturer producing goods only and constitute one of the elements of the businessman. While in Law No. 8 of 1999 on Consumer Protection used the term business communities. Article 1 Point 3 Consumer Protection Law, understanding business agent formulated as follows: "Any individual or business entity, whether a legal entity and not a legal entity established and domiciled in the territory of the Republic of Indonesia, either alone mapun together through treaty implementation of the activities businesses in various economic fields".

Service users is another term for consumers who specifically intended for users of transport modes, whether land, sea or air. Because it is another name for the consumer, then the consumer rights set out in Law No. 8 of 1999 on Consumer Protection also applies to users of transportation services in Indonesia.

Consumer rights are regulated under the Consumer Protection Law (BFL) contained in Article 4, which reads:

- a. The right to comfort, security and safety. , , ,
- b. , , , ,
- c. The right to information is correct, clear and honest. , , ,
- d. The right to be heard opinions and complaints. , , ,
- e. Entitlement to advocacy, protection, and mediation in consumer protection are worth;
- f. , , , ,
- g. The right to be treated or serviced properly and honestly and not discriminatory;
- h. The right to obtain compensation, compensation and / or replacement. , , ,
- i. The rights set forth in the provisions of other legislation

The rights of users of air transport services last once regulated in Law No. 1 of 2009 on Flight, where the rights of users of transportation services is in the form of:

2.1.1 The Right to Get Services

Act No. 1 of 2009 on Flight contained in Article 97 regulates air transport services. Air transport services in Indonesia are divided into three (3) parts, namely:

- a. Standard of service with a maximum (full services); The maximum is a form of service provided to passengers during the flight in accordance with the type of service class flight.
- b. Service with a standard medium (media services); which forms the simple services provided to passengers.
- c. Service with the minimum standards (no frills) is a form of minimum service provided to passengers.

In addition to getting services within the meaning of Article 97 of the decent service is also provided to the users of transportation services for the disabled, elderly, children and / or sick as stipulated in Article 134 of Law No. 1 of 2009 on Penerbanagan are entitled to treatment services and special amenities such as:

- a. Provision of additional priority seating;
- b. Provision of facilities for the ease of riding onto and off of the aircraft;
- c. Provision of facilities for the disabled while in the aircraft;
- d. Aids for the sick;
- e. Provision of facilities for children while in the aircraft;
- f. The availability of personnel who can communicate with the disabled, the elderly, children, and / or sick; and
- g. Availability of manual safety and aviation security for air travelers and other means that can be understood by people with the CACT, the elderly, and the sick;

In addition to the articles mentioned above, the rights for users of air transport services contained in Article 140 of Law Flight that essentially require the air carrier providing the proper service to every user of air transport services.

2.1.2 Right to Obtain Compensation

In addition to getting the right care of the air carrier, the transport services also earn the right to get compensation from the carrier if the transport service users suffer losses due to improper air carrier. The carrier compensation is a form of responsibility that must be done by the air carrier for damages suffered by passengers.

Regarding the responsibility (some literature uses the term accountability as the translation of the liability, are included in this article uses the term liability) the air carrier is known some of the principles of accountability.

The principle of accountability is a subject that is very important in consumer protection law (in this paper uses the term as a synonym transport service consumer). In general, the principles of accountability in law can be distinguished as follows:

- 1) Error (liability based on fault), Fault liability or liability based on fault is fairly common principle applies in criminal and civil law. This principle states, the new person should be held legally accountable lawsuit if there is an element of error does.
"The definition of error is an element that is against the law. Definition of "law" is not only contrary to the law, but also decency and morality in society".
By common sense, the principle of accountability is unacceptable because it is unfair for people who do wrong to compensate for the victim and very unfair if an innocent person should replace the losses suffered by others.
- 2) The presumption is always accountable (presumption of liability); This principle states, a defendant is always considered to be accountable, until he can prove he is innocent. Thus, the burden of proof is on the defendant.

Relating to the principle of accountability, in particular the transport legal doctrine, known four variations:

- a) The carrier can break free from liability if it can prove losses caused by matters beyond his control;
- b) The carrier may exempt itself from liability if he can prove he take a necessary action to avoid losses;
- c) The carrier can free yourself liability if he can prove, losses incurred through no fault;
- d) The carrier is not accountable if the loss was caused by an error / passenger negligence or because of the quality / quality of goods transported is not good.

Looks burden of proof reversed (*omkering van bewijslast*) received in these principles. The rationale of the theory of the reversal of the burden of proof is a person is considered innocent until concerned can prove otherwise. This is contrary to the legal principle of presumption of, which is commonly known in the law. However, if the applied nature of cases the transport services will appear, such principle is quite relevant. If this theory is applied, then it is obliged to prove that there is an error on the part of businesses (air transport) who sued.

- 1) The presumption is always not accountable (presumption of nonliability); This principle is known only in a very limited scope of the transaction, and such restrictions are common sense usually can be justified.
- 2) Accountability absolute (strict liability); this principle is identified with the principle of absolute liability, although there is also an opinion that differentiate the two terms. Some argue that strict liability is a principle of accountability that sets the error is not a decisive factor. However, there are exceptions that allow exempting from liability, e.g. the object force majeure. In contrast, absolute liability is the principle of liability without fault and no exceptions. In addition, there is a view somewhat similar to that linked both to the existing differences and in the absence of a causal relationship between the subjects accountable and guilt. On strict liability, the relationship that should exist, whiles the

absolute liability of the relationship was not always there.³ That is, the absolute liability of the defendants can be held accountable lawsuit was not the direct perpetrators of the error.

R.C. Hoerber et.al says that, usually absolute liability principle is applied because:

- a) service users are not in an advantageous position to prove the existence of errors in a complex process and distribution;
- b) Assumed to be Able to Anticipate the manufacturer at any time if there is a lawsuit for his mistake, for example by insurance or adding Certain components of cost in the product price;
- c) This principle can force manufacturers are more cautious.
 - 1) Restriction of liability (limitation of liability). This principle is very loved by the carrier to be included as an exoneration clause in the standard agreement made. This principle is usually combined with the principles of accountability other, namely Article 17 Paragraph (1) Guatemala Protocol of 1971, the principle of accountability to the restrictions associated with the principle of absolute liability.

This principle is extremely detrimental to the freight when stipulated unilaterally by the carrier. Therefore, the carrier should not be allowed to unilaterally determine the adverse clause transport service users, including limiting the maximum liability lawsuit.

In addition to the right to redress, the air transport services are also entitled to ask for accountability carrier caused delays transported by carrier transport modes. Likewise, the service user cannot be transported by a carrier aircraft with a capacity reasons. In this case the carrier must compensate the service user in the form of:⁴

- a) Divert the flight to another without having to pay additional fees; and / or
- b) Giving consumption, accommodation, and transportation costs if there is no other flight to destination.

Relating to responsibility (accountability) air carrier in Indonesia, as the reference is Law No. 1 of 2009 on Flight governing liability carrier to passengers of Article 141, Article 146 and Pasal147. Article 141 regulates air carrier liability for damages of passengers who died permanent disability, or injuries resulting from the incident of air transport in the plane and / or up and down aircraft.

Article 146 of Law No. 1 of 2009 governing the liability of air carriers for losses suffered due to the delay in the transport of passengers, baggage or cargo; unless the carrier can prove that the delay is caused by weather and technical factor operational.

While Article 147 regulates air carrier liability over lifting can no passengers, According to the schedule determined by the capacity of the aircraft. Form of responsibility in the form of water transferred to other flights of the carrier without paying an additional fee; and/or provides consumption, accommodation, and transportation costs if there is no other flight to the destination.

The implementation of Law No. 1 Year 2009 on The flight, in particular to the responsibilities of air conveyance, the Government of the Republic of Indonesia in this case the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia on August 8, 2011 issued Regulation of the Minister of Communications No. 77 Year 2011 on Liability Carrier Air Transport. The provisions contained in Article 141, 146 and 147 of Law No. 1 of 2009 implemented in Article 3, Article 9, Article 10, Article 11, Article 12 and Article 13 of the Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 Year 2011 The.

Implementation of Article 141 of Law No. 1 of 2009 contained in Article 3 of the Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia stated that for harm to passengers who died in an aircraft as an aircraft accident or incident solely to do with the air transport awarded damages Rp 1,250,000,000, - (one billion two hundred fifty million rupiah) per passenger.

³ Az Nasution, 1995, Consumers and the Law: Review of Social Economics and Law On Protection of Consumer Indonesia, Pustaka Sinar Harapan, Jakarta, p 72.

⁴ Article 147 paragraph (2) of Law No. 1 Year 2009 on Aviation.

Passengers who died during embarkation and disembarkation process, both at the airport of destination and transit at the airport given compensation amounting to Rp 500.000.000, - (five hundred million rupiah).

For passengers who Suffered permanent disability awarded damages amounting to Rp 1,250,000,000, - (one million two hundred fifty million rupiah) per passenger, while for Injured passengers were awarded compensation for the cost of care and the highest real Rp 200.000.000, - (two hundred million rupiah).

The provisions of Article 146 and Article 147 of Law No. 1 of 2009 on Flights can be seen in the implementation of Article 9, 10, 11, 12 and Article 13 of the Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 Year 2011 on Liability Carrier Air Transport.

Article 9 is essentially regulates air transport delays consist of flight delayed, denied boarding passenger, and cancelation of flight. The amount of compensation for passengers delayed due to flight of four hours or more of Rp 300,000, - (three hundred thousand rupiah) per passenger. For delays caused by denied boarding passenger, the carrier must transfer to other flights without paying additional costs and / or provide consumption, accommodation, and transportation costs if there is no other flight to the destination. As for passengers who experience cancelation of flight under Article 12, which essentially set when a flight cancellation, the carrier shall inform the passengers at least 7 (seven) calendar days prior to the flight ticket to return all the money that has been paid by the passenger.

Article 13 Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 Year 2011 concerning the release of the air carrier to compensation due to flight delays if caused by weather factors and / or operational techniques. Weather factors, among others, in the form of rain, lightning, storms, fog, smoke, visibility below the standards that interfere with flight safety. While the definition of technical and operational factors, among others airport for departure and destination cannot be used operational aircraft, airport or runway environment towards impaired function due to cracks, flood, or fire. Technical operating companies can also be the caused because of the queue of aircraft taking off and landing, or departure time slot or also due to refueling.

2.2 Field Results

Besides using literature data, this study also uses field data gained through the researcher's own experience as well as interviews with some of the passengers who had experienced air transport issues.

Field data presented in this paper relates to the right of good service to passengers and the right to compensation if the loss in air transport.

2.2.1 Rights Service Excellence

Article 134 of Law No. 1 of 2009 on flights by expressly granting special services such as treatment and special facilities for the disabled, elderly, children under 12 (twelve) years, and the sick from business entities air transport. Minimum service facilities and special services are specifically named in Section 134 subsection (2) of Law No. 1 Year 2009 on Aviation. A description of the special facilities such a reference researchers in conducting research and results are described as follows:

- a) Provision of additional priority seats for the disabled, the elderly, children under the age of twelve (12) years, and for the sick. This facility is not found inside the aircraft on domestic flights. People with disabilities such as passengers who cannot walk at the time of embarkation and disembarkation only helped a wheelchair pushed by airline personnel. Special chair prescribed legislation is not found in the airplane, even to be able to sit in a place that helps ease for passengers with disabilities, usually on the sincerity of the other passengers gave his seat used by the passengers with disabilities. During the study, researchers did not find a lack of coordination between the officers of airlines serving check-in with the families of passengers with disabilities is to be given the seat which makes it easier for those with disabilities.

The elderly by Act No. 1 of 2009 to get priority seating in the airplane are not found in domestic flights in Indonesia. Passengers are elderly and often given a seat at the rear of the

aircraft, which is of course the conditions of the less convenient for passengers elderly due to the type of aircraft operating in Indonesia, more use of Boeing and Airbus that the engine is in the back of the plane so that cause aircraft engine noise quite annoying passengers.

Passengers are children under the age of 12 (twelve) years should get the service a special seat on the plane is treated the same as adults, Just the which distinguishes that children under three (3) years-provided a seat belt itself, rest facilities together, Including ticket prices for children above 2 (two) years is equal to the price of an adult ticket, while Tickets for children under two (2) years to be paid half of the adult fare.

As for the special facilities such as special seating for the sick for domestic flights in Indonesia is not provided. For sick people who use the gurney caused by conditions that do not allow sitting down, then the sick passengers will not be transported by the airline regularly, but they must charter an aircraft to and from the destination.

- b) Provision of facilities for the ease of riding onto and off of the aircraft; such facilities in all aircraft on domestic flights cannot be found, possibly because due to the type of aircraft operating in Indonesia are not equipped with special facilities to ascend to and descend from the aircraft. Air passengers with disabilities, such as passengers who cannot walk when going up and down from the aircraft, or when using *garbarata* (trunk), passengers who cannot walk are in the lap by personnel carrier for seated on seat passengers and thus also wanted to get off the plane while passengers in the lap by airline personnel and seated in a wheelchair and then pushed toward the exit the arrivals building.
- c) Provision of facilities for the disabled while in an aircraft; all aircraft operating in Indonesia do not have special facilities on board the aircraft for the disabled. This is because the type of aircraft operating in Indonesia classified as aircraft type medium since the number of seats of the aircraft only a maximum of 210 seats namely Boeing 900 ER. Types of commercial aircraft operating in Indonesia almost entirely for business purposes only, therefore the number of seats was made in such a way that can accommodate passengers in large numbers, without regard to special facilities predetermined legislation.
- d) Aids for the sick; for passengers who are gravely ill, no special aids contained in a commercial plane in Indonesia. Similarly, passengers with disabilities, the elderly, are not provided special means as befits the order of legislation. If the ill passenger who wanted to depart with the use of special facilities, then the passengers themselves must charter plane, which is of course the cost is very expensive.
- e) Provision of facilities for children while in the aircraft; for children passengers under the age of 12 (twelve) years cannot be found in a special facility for aircraft. Existing facilities are for passengers under the age of 2 (two) years is given using a small seat belt separate from the existing seat belts in every seat passenger. After the aircraft arrived at the destination, then a special seat belt is returned to the clerk aircraft.
- f) The availability of personnel who can communicate with the disabled, the elderly, children, and / or sick; for passengers with disabilities, the elderly and children under the age of 12 (twelve) years are not provided specialized personnel who can communicate with them. Passengers mentioned above when traveling by using the aircraft, then it must be accompanied by his family, or medical personnel such as doctors and nurses who become dependent passengers themselves.
- g) Availability of manual safety and aviation security for air travelers and other means that can be understood by people with disabilities, the elderly. Guide on aviation safety and security are generally supplied in the plane located at each passenger seat. Crew demonstrate how to use safety belts, masks, and protective time of the accident.

2.2.2 Right to Compensation if Experiencing Losses

Air passengers in Indonesia under Law No. 1 of 2009 on Flight granted the right to compensation if the losses. Article 141, paragraph (1), Article 146 and Article 147 of Law No. 1 of 2009 ordered all airlines to be responsible for losses suffered by passengers in the event :

- a) Passengers died; follow up to the provisions of Article 141 (1) of Law No. 1 of 2009 on this Flight, Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia issued Regulation No. 77 Year 2011 on Liability Carrier Air Transport. In this ministerial regulation, if a passenger died in a plane crash caused by aircraft, then get a compensation of Rp 1,250,000,000, - (one billion two hundred fifty million rupiah). In practice, compensation is provided by the air carrier to the heirs of the victim with a very complicated procedure and quite a long time. An example is the case of aircraft accidents Indonesia Air Asia flight code QZ 8501 Route Juanda Surabaya to Singapore's Changi Airport at 07:55 West Indonesia Time December 28, 2014. The process of compensation for passengers who died until now has not been completed by the Air Asia Indonesia. In awarding damages amounting to Rp 1,250,000,000, - (one billion two hundred fifty million) rupiah, the air carrier cannot escape, since Article 141 (1) of Law No. 1 of 2009 applying the principle of Absolute Liability. Thus, the carrier must pay compensation for passengers who died.
- b) Passengers permanent disability; passengers who suffered permanent disability by a doctor within the period of 60 (sixty) days after the occurrence of aircraft accidents to get compensation amounting to Rp 1,250,000,000, - (one billion two hundred fifty million) rupiah. Total permanent disability here as vision loss total of the two eyes that cannot be cured, or breaking two hands or two feet or one hand and one foot or above the wrist or leg, or vision loss total of the eye which cannot be cured and the dissolution of the hand or foot above the wrist or ankle.

As for passengers who declared partial permanent disability by a physician within the period of 60 (sixty) days after the occurrence of an aircraft accident are given compensation varies depending on the handicap suffered. This provision up to this writing there has been no accident aircraft aboard survived.

- c) Passengers injured; passengers who were injured and had to undergo treatment at a hospital, clinic or clinic as an inpatient or outpatient awarded compensation for the real cost of care at most Rp 200.000.000, - (two hundred million rupiah). In practice, there are no passengers who experience this situation, because since the enactment of the Minister of Communications No. 77 of 2011 in Indonesia has not been accidents aircraft aboard survived.
- d) Passengers delayed; in practice, passengers who experienced delays of more than four (4) hours are given compensation amounting to Rp 300,000, - (three hundred thousand) rupiah. However, the money given by the airline no cash, there are also given in the form of a transfer to an account in the name of the passenger. Giving by transfer to an account in the name of passengers is very detrimental to passengers because there is no realization of how this kind of compensation.

Loss of passengers who experience delays of less than 4 (four) hours in practice for this is if the delay was less than an hour, the passengers get food and soft drinks, whereas if the delay is more than one hour and less than three hours, every passenger getting consumption of food (lunch boxes) and drink.

The reason given for this by the airline is the delay caused by weather factors and / or due to technical and operational.

- e) Flight cancellations; for losses caused by the cancellation of flights during this time due to natural factors such as the eruption of volcanoes, smoke factor resulting in low visibility resulting in the cancellation of the flight. Passengers are given the option that, refunded the entire ticket, or waiting for a flight at an uncertain time. For passengers who choose to divert departure using a mix of transport modes such as the most used mode of transport by land, sea and air, then entirely be borne by the air carrier.

Flight cancellations like this not only result in losses for the passengers, but also very detrimental to the airline because his aircraft could not fly due to volcanic eruption and resulting smog.

3. Conclusions and Recommendations

3.1 Conclusions

From the whole description above, it can be concluded as follows:

- a) Legislation on good service to passengers who are disabled, elderly, children under the age of 12 (twelve) years old and the sick to get a special facility of a business entity is not found in the cost of domestic air transportation in Indonesia.
- b) The procedure to get compensation to the passengers who died as a result of aircraft accidents in Indonesia is very convoluted.
- c) The compensation to air passengers in Indonesia are caused by the delay has not been optimally implemented, especially against the granting of damages as a result of delay in departure of more than four hours.

3.2 Recommendations

- a) That the Government of the Republic of Indonesia issued a regulation imposing sanctions against airlines that do not provide special facilities in the mode of air transport for passengers with disabilities, the elderly, children under the age of 12 (twelve) years old and the sick.
- b) That the Government of the Republic of Indonesia to make regulations concerning the acceleration of the provision of compensation to passengers as a result of plane crash in Indonesia.
- c) In order for the Ministry of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia to supervise the implementation of the Regulation of the Minister of Transport of the Republic of Indonesia Number 77 Year 2011 on Liability Carrier Air Transport.

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